

FIELD SCREENING AND IDENTIFICATION OF SCAB RESISTANT COWPEA VARIETIES

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ABSTRACT

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) is an essential crop in sub-Saharan Africa, providing dietary protein and improving soil fertility (Olufajo and Akinwunmi, 2022). However, Cowpea scab, caused by *Sphaceloma* sp. significantly affects yield in cowpea. This study aimed to screen nine cowpea varieties for scab resistance and identify those with high resistance or susceptibility. The nine varieties of Cowpea were screened under artificial inoculation with the scab pathogen and field conditions to select highly resistance and susceptible varieties. Data was collected on disease incidence and severity and subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) at a p-value of 0.05 significance. Varieties IT99K-573-1-1 and TVx-3236 showed strong resistance, while FUAMPEA-4 and UAM-09-130-20-4 were highly susceptible. Cluster analysis grouped varieties based on their resistance profiles, and significant differences in scab resistance were observed. The dendrogram generated from the cluster analysis, shows a clear grouping of the cowpea varieties based on disease incidence and severity into four distinct clusters. The grouping shows the genetic relationships and differences among the cowpea varieties in their resistance to scab. Results from this study provide valuable information for breeding scab-resistant cowpea varieties.

Keywords: Cowpea, Scab Resistance, *Sphaceloma* sp., Field Screening, Disease Incidence, Disease Severity

INTRODUCTION

Cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.] is an indigenous leafy vegetable and a grain legume widely grown in the semiarid areas of sub-Saharan Africa (Da Silva et al 2019). The importance of cowpea in this region stems from its drought tolerance and

ability to grow under water stress conditions (Carvalho et al., 2017), and its crucial role in ensuring food security and supporting the livelihoods of millions of smallholder farmers who depend on it for their economic and nutritional well-being (Bolarinwa, 2022). The nutritional value

of cowpea stems from its high protein content (25%) (Ogbonnaya *et al.*, 2003; Mekonnen *et al.*, 2022), which plays a considerable role in balancing the predominantly carbohydrate-based nutrition of the rural population in the West Africa subregion (Krasova-Wade *et al.*, 2006; Singh *et al.*, 2022). Cowpea is also an integral part of a sustainable agriculture and land use system (Ogbonnaya *et al.*, 2003) and an essential component of traditional intercropping systems (Singh, 2002). Integration of cowpea in cropping systems promotes buildup of soil organic matter and carbon and nitrogen fixation and ultimately improves soil fertility physical characteristics such as the water infiltration and retention capacity (Sánchez-Navarro *et al.*, 2019a,b).

Cowpea is grown on about 14, 911, 307 million hectares worldwide, with an annual grain production of about 8, 986, 191.25 million tons (FAO, 2021). Nigeria produced about 3, 628, 612.65 million tons of cowpea, making her the world largest producer; followed by Niger (2, 661, 882.93 million tons), Burkina Faso (705, 768.3 tons) and Kenya (250, 260 tons) (FAO, 2021). In Nigeria, cowpea is predominately grown in the drier northern parts of the country; however, advances in crop development have opened opportunities for its production in the wetter agroecologies (Nwofia *et al.*, 2006), with the north-central guinea savanna zone contributing 29% production in 2020 (NAERLS, 2020).

Although the West African sub-region accounts for over 95% of world cowpea production (Samireddypalle *et al.*, 2017), its production has largely been due to increase in land mass rather than productivity per unit area. Studies have shown that the yield from farmers' fields is very low (500 kg/ha) compared to that obtained in the USA (2000 kg/ha) and in Australia (2200 kg/ha) (Quin, 1997). The low yield is attributed to

the effect of several biotic and abiotic factors (Omoigui *et al.*, 2007). However, biotic stresses like cowpea scab disease, caused by *Sphaceloma sp.* (Emechebe *et al.*, 1997), threaten cowpea production. The disease affects all above-ground parts of the cowpea plant, including leaves, stems, pod and severe infections can lead to significant yield losses (Afutu *et al.*, 2016). Effective management of this disease relies on identifying resistant varieties. The identification of scab-resistant and susceptible cowpea varieties using morphological analysis will provide reliable information that crop scientists can leverage to develop resistant varieties for this destructive disease. This study focuses on screening cowpea varieties for scab resistance under field conditions to identify resistant and susceptible lines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Materials, Experimental Design and Location.

Nine cowpea varieties (FUAMPEA-4, Gujarat Cowpea-3, Gujarat Cowpea-5, Gujarat Cowpea-6, IT99K-573-1-1, Pant Lobia-4, Pant Lobia-1, TVx-3236, and UAM-09-130-20-4) were used. They were obtained from the cowpea breeding program of the Molecular Biology Laboratory, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi, from the Germplasm of the Stress Tolerant Orphan Legume (STOL) project comprising Germplasm from Nigeria and India.

The field experiment was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University of Agriculture, Makurdi, following a randomized complete block design with three replications. The field was laid out in plots according to the experimental design. Each plot consisted of a single row, 4 m long, and seeds were sown at an intra-row spacing of

25cm, resulting into 16 hills and 32 plants per plot.

Cultural Practices

At sowing, Pendimethalin, a pre-emergence herbicide was applied to subdue weeds until crop establishment. The herbicide was applied at a dilution of 150 mls per 20 litre knapsack sprayer.

Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium were applied in the form of NPK 15:15:15 fertilizer at the rate of 100kg/ha. This is the equivalent of 0.075kg (75g) per plot, applied by side placement as a single dose at one week (7 days) after planting (7 DAP). Weeding was done manually and it was carried out for all plots at 3 weeks (21 days) after planting and subsequently as needed to keep the field free from weeds till maturity. Cypermethrine + Dimethoate was sprayed at the rate of 50 g a.i/ ha to control insect pests.

Pathogen Inoculation

Cowpea plants were inoculated with *Sphaceloma* sp. isolated from samples of infected plant materials collected from the cowpea breeding field of the Molecular Biology Laboratory, at the Research Farm of the College of Agronomy, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi, at 14 days post-planting, and disease incidence and severity were recorded at intervals. The spores suspension for inoculation was prepared at the Crop and Environmental Protection Laboratory as described by Afutu *et al.* (2016). The concentration of spores in the solution was determined using a hemocytometer, and adjusted to 10^5 spores/mL for the inoculation.

Cowpea plants were artificially inoculated with scab disease by spraying the spore

suspension of *Sphaceloma* sp onto the plants at the flower initiation stage. The inoculum was applied to the plants' canopy with a hand-held sprayer until runoff at 14 DAP. After inoculation, water spray was applied to plants in the evening to maintain high humidity for disease development.

Data Collection and Statistical Analysis

Observations were made on a plot by plot basis, on the incidence and severity of scab infection. Disease incidence and severity were assessed at 14 days post-inoculation (DPI) and then every 7 days after, up to 28 DPI.

According to Afutu *et al.* (2016), the symptoms of cowpea scab disease caused by *Sphaceloma* sp. include:

1. Small, circular, dark brown to black spots or lesions on the leaves, stems, and pods.
2. Lesions may merge to form larger, irregularly shaped spots.
3. Spots may have a reddish-brown border and a grayish center.
4. Severe infections can lead to defoliation, reduced pod formation, and lower yields.

Disease incidence was measured as the percentage of plants showing symptoms of scab infection (Gerstman, 2015) as shown below:

$$\text{Incidence (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of infected plants}}{\text{Total number of plants}} \times 100$$

Disease severity was determined using a rating scale of 1 to 10, with 1 indicating minimal infection and 10 indicating severe infection (Gerstman, 2015). The disease severity scale is as follows:

- 0: No symptoms
- 1: 1-10% infection
- 2: 11-20% infection
- 3: 21-30% infection
- 4: 31-40% infection
- 5: 41-50% infection
- 6: 51-60% infection

- 7: 61-70% infection
 8: 71-80% infection
 9: 81-90% infection
 10: 91-100% infection (plant death)

The disease severity index was determined using the following formula (Gafni et al., 2015)

$$DSI = \left[\frac{\sum (\text{disease rating} \times \text{number of plants in the rating})}{\text{Total number of plants scored} \times \text{maximum disease class}} \right] \times 100$$

Where:

Disease rating=The severity rating assigned to plants using the rating scale

Number of plants in the class=The number of plants counted in the rating scale

Total number of plants scored = The total number of plants evaluated for the disease

Maximum disease class = highest possible value on the rating scale.

Data were analyzed using GenStat software, Seventeenth Edition (VSN International, 2016). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to determine the significance of differences among varieties for both incidence and severity of cowpea scab. ANOVA is a suitable statistical tool for comparing multiple groups (varieties) to determine if significant differences exist. Duncan's Multiple Range Test was used for mean separation where significant differences were found. Hierarchical cluster analysis was conducted using Minitab software (Minitab Inc., 2022), to group the varieties based on their disease resistance profiles. Euclidean distance and complete linkage methods were used to create dendrogram representing the similarity levels among the varieties. The analysis involved the calculation of similarity and distance levels among the varieties, amalgamation of clusters based on the calculated distances and determination of the number of clusters based on within-cluster sum of squares and

average and maximum distances from centroid.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The summary of ANOVA in this study for the incidence and severity of scab infection is presented in Table 1. The result showed a significant difference among the varieties ($p < 0.001$) in the incidence and severity of scab infection among the cowpea varieties tested. The p-value ($p < 0.001$) indicates a very low probability of observing the differences by chance, showing that the results are reliable. The significant difference among varieties indicates genetic variation in resistance to scab infection. This suggests that some cowpea varieties are more resistant or susceptible to scab infection than others. Understanding variety-specific resistance can inform integrated disease management strategies, and aid in breeding programs to develop scab-resistant cowpea cultivars. Similar results have been reported by other researchers such as Jorem *et al.* (2023), who evaluated 390 cowpea varieties for resistance to scab and found significant differences among varieties ($p < 0.001$) using ANOVA. Afutu *et al.* (2016) also screened 100 cowpea varieties and identified resistant and susceptible lines using ANOVA ($p < 0.001$). These studies demonstrate the effectiveness of ANOVA in identifying genetic variation in cowpea resistance to scab infection.

Table 1: Mean Squares from Analysis of Variance for Disease Severity and Incidence for 9 Cowpea varieties

Source of Variation	df	Incidence	Severity
Rep	2	4.481ns	0.36111ns
Variety	8	2626.954**	14.22917**
Error	16	5.940	0.06944
Total	26		

** = Highly significant difference among cowpea varieties for disease severity and incidence at a 99% probability level; ns = no significant difference among replications for disease severity and incidence at a 99% probability level

Table 2 also shows that 9 cowpea varieties evaluated for their reaction to scab infection showed varied reactions in terms of disease incidence and severity measurement. The variety FUAMPEA-4 and UAM-09-130-20-4 showed the highest incidence at 71.67%, while IT99K-573-1-1 and TVx-3236 exhibited the lowest incidence at 1%. All the cowpea varieties recorded disease severity scores greater than 5, except for IT99K-573-1-1 and TVx-3236. The variety UAM-09-130-20-4 had the highest severity score of 6.7, followed by Pant Lobia-1 with a score of 6.2, while IT99K-573-1-1 and TVx-3236 showed the lowest severity score of 1.

This result indicates that FUAMPEA-4 and UAM-09-130-20-4 were susceptible to scab caused by *Sphaceloma sp.* while IT99K-573-1-1 and TVx-3236 were resistance. In similar studies, variations in susceptibility to cowpea scab caused by *Sphaceloma sp.* have been observed, with some varieties demonstrating higher levels of resistance. This variability in resistance likely stems from genetic differences between the varieties, specifically in genes that confer resistance to the disease. This aligns with the findings of Ayodele *et al.*

(2020), who reported that disease severity and incidence in cowpea vary depending on the genetic makeup of the varieties tested, environmental conditions, and the virulence of the pathogen.

Previous studies, such as by Ayo-Vaughan *et al.* (2016) and Emechebe *et al.* (2000), have shown that IT99K-573-1-1 has strong resistance to multiple stresses, including bacterial blight and nematodes, which further supports its strong resistance to scab in this study. Similarly, studies by Boukar *et al.* (2018) have highlighted the importance of genetic resistance in cowpea breeding, especially for biotic stresses like bacterial blight and fungal pathogens, where resistant lines like TVx-3236 have been used as donors for resistance traits.

The clear contrast between susceptible and resistant varieties in terms of incidence and severity scores underscores the breeding potential of varieties like IT99K-573-1-1 and TVx-3236. These resistant varieties can be incorporated into cowpea improvement programs, particularly through Marker-Assisted Selection (MAS), where specific resistance genes can be tracked and introgressed into susceptible but high-yielding varieties.

The role of MAS in speeding up the breeding process, allowing breeders to develop new varieties that can withstand biotic stresses, thereby improving crop resilience and food security has been emphasised (Timko *et al.*, 2007).

Table 2: Mean Disease Incidence and Severity Response of 9 Cowpea varieties to Scab infection

Variety	Mean Incidence (%)	Mean Severity (1-10)
FUAMPEA-4	71.67	5.67
UAM-09-130-20-4	71.67	6.67
Gujarat Cowpea-3	53.33	5.33
Gujarat Cowpea-5	15.00	6.00
Gujarat Cowpea-6	13.67	5.50
Pant Lobia-4	11.67	5.67
Pant Lobia-1	6.67	6.17
IT99K-573-1-1	1	1
TVx-3236	1	1
Standard Error (SE)	1.41	0.15

Tables 3, 4, and 5 show the results of the cluster analysis using the Euclidean distance and complete linkage method grouped. The varieties are grouped into four distinct clusters based on their scab resistance. The cluster centroids indicate a clear separation between highly resistant and susceptible varieties.

Cluster 1 comprises only one variety with moderate disease incidence and severity. This suggests an intermediate response to scab, possibly indicating that the variety has some level of resistance but is not as robust as those in the more resistant clusters.

Cluster 2 contains four varieties with low incidence and moderate severity. These varieties may possess resistance to disease progression but still exhibit some susceptibility. The moderate severity suggests that while they can limit disease spread, they may not fully prevent damage, which can be linked to partial resistance genes or environmental interactions

influencing resistance expression. This is consistent with other studies where moderate resistance has been observed in certain cowpea lines during disease screening (Boukar *et al.*, 2018).

Cluster 3 includes two varieties with very low incidence and severity, indicating strong resistance to the disease. These varieties are ideal candidates for breeding programs, as they likely possess robust resistance genes that can be utilized in developing new resistant cowpea lines. Varieties in this cluster could be considered for use in Marker-Assisted Selection (MAS), helping breeders pyramid resistance genes, as suggested by Timko *et al.* (2007).

Cluster 4 contains two varieties with high incidence and severity, marking them as susceptible. These varieties likely lack resistance genes to the strain of scab used in this study. High susceptibility has been documented in various cowpea varieties under specific disease pressures, as seen in studies by Singh and Emechebe (1997).

Table 3. Final Cluster Partition of cowpea Varieties Screened

Cluster	Number of Observations	Within Cluster Sum of Squares	Average Distance from Centroid	Maximum Distance from Centroid
1	1	0.00	0.00000	0.00000
2	4	69.25	3.76329	6.26997
3	2	0.00	0.00000	0.00000
4	2	0.50	0.50000	0.50000

Table 4. Cluster Centroids

Variable	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Grand Centroid
Incidence (%)	55.0	11.25	1	70	26.8889
Severity (1-10)	5.5	5.50	1	6	4.6111

Table 5. Distances between Cluster Centroids

Cluster	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Cluster 1	0.0000	43.7500	54.1872	15.0083
Cluster 2	43.7500	0.0000	11.1943	58.7521
Cluster 3	54.1872	11.1943	0.0000	69.1809
Cluster 4	15.0083	58.7521	69.1809	0.0000

Figure 1 is the dendrogram illustrating the similarity among the cowpea varieties based on their scab incidence and severity. The dendrogram generated from the cluster analysis, shows a clear grouping of the

cowpea varieties based on disease incidence and severity into four distinct clusters. The grouping shows the genetic relationships and differences among the cowpea varieties in their resistance to scab

Figure 2. Dendrogram illustrating the similarity among the cowpea varieties based on their scab incidence and severity

The separation of the varieties into distinct clusters highlights the diversity in genetic resistance to scab in cowpea, making this clustering crucial for selection. Breeders can focus on varieties from Cluster 3 for future breeding programs aimed at improving disease resistance. Other researchers such as Agbicodo *et al.* (2010), used cluster analysis to evaluate cowpea response to biotic and abiotic stresses, demonstrating the utility of this technique for understanding genetic relationships between cowpea varieties.

CONCLUSION

This study successfully identified significant genetic variability in scab resistance among nine cowpea varieties.

IT99K-573-1-1 and TVx-3236 are highly resistant and suitable for breeding programs aimed at improving scab resistance in cowpea. The findings from this study contribute to ongoing efforts to enhance cowpea productivity, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, where the crop is vital for food security and livelihoods.

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